

STUDIES IN BACTERIAL AMYLASES. PART I. EFFECT OF DIFFERENT FORMS OF NITROGEN ON THE FORMATION OF AMYLASE IN BACTERIA

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Different sources of nitrogen in the formation of bacterial amylase employing the strain N.C.T.C., 2027 N (allied to *B. subtilis*) have been investigated. Among the sources of nitrogen tried, ammonium lactate has been found to be the best enzyme-former. Aeration has been found to augment the yield of amylase considerably.

Amylases constitute an industrially important and widely distributed group of enzymes. Among the various sources of amylase, bacteria constitute the best available source for the manufacture of the enzyme.

Bacterial amylases, which generally have a higher content of the liquefying fraction (α -amylase component) and which are capable of functioning at higher optimal temperatures and reactions, are eminently suited to be employed for the desizing of the textiles and other allied processes in textile industry.

A systematic enquiry was therefore directed towards elucidating the nutritional factors and the cultural conditions which influence the formation of amylase in certain types of bacteria in general, and in a particularly highly amylolytic strain of bacteria.

The effect of different forms of nitrogen on the formation of amylase in bacteria was investigated by several workers (Wallerstein, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1939, **31**, 1278; Tilden and Hudson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2139; Beckord *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, **37**, 692; Peltier and Beckord, *J. Bact.*, 1945, **50**, 711; Hockenfull and Herbert, *J. Biochem.*, 1945, **39**, 102; Beckord *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1946, **38**, 232; *Arch. Biochem.*, 1946, **10**, 41). These workers generally used the organic and complex forms of nitrogen in the culture media using organisms of *subtilis*, *polymyxa*, *macerans* etc. groups in relation to the formation of bacterial amylases. Mostly the work was conducted with the extracts of proteinaceous materials, either of vegetable or animal origin, but in some cases organic forms of nitrogen, like peptone, etc. were employed.

The importance of the availability of a suitable form of nitrogen in the culture medium was emphasised by Boidin and Efront (U.S. Patent, 1,227,374; 1,225,525; 1937). Systematic work on the efficiency of different forms of nitrogen on the formation of amylase, employing one single organism, has been found to be lacking.

The present paper relates to investigations on the different sources of nitrogen in the formation of bacterial amylase employing the strain N.C.T.C., 2027 N, very much allied to *Bacillus subtilis*.

EXPERIMENTAL

Selection of the strain of Bacillus Subtilis.—About 30 different strains of *Bacillus subtilis* reported to possess diastogenic activity were obtained from the National Collection of Type Cultures, India. These strains were screened on nutrient agar medium, previously incorporated with 0.2% of soluble starch. The extent of their amylolytic

activities was determined qualitatively by flooding the screens with *N/200*-iodine solution, when measurable, clear and unstained zones around each of the colonies were secured; the one which gave the highest clearance zone was selected for these investigations.

The organism carries the number N.C.T.C., 2027 N in the repository of the National Collection of Type Cultures, India.

Preparation of the Inoculum.—The inoculum was prepared by transferring a loop of the culture from a nutrient agar slant to a tube containing 5 ml. of nutrient broth; the tube was then incubated at 37° in a slanting position on a wooden rack. After 24 hours' incubation, the tube was centrifuged till all the bacterial cells settled at the bottom. The clear supernatant layer was poured out and the cells were repeatedly washed on the centrifuge with sterilized *N/15*-phosphate solution and the bacterial residue was finally made up to 25 ml. with the phosphate solution; 0.5 ml. of this inoculum was used throughout these investigations.

Evaluation of Starch-liquefying Activity.—The liquefying power of the enzyme sample was determined by viscometric method. The reaction mixtures consisted of 15 ml. of the 2% starch solution, buffered to a p_H of 7.0 and 1.0 ml. of the enzyme preparation; the total volume of the reaction mixture was 16.0 ml. Each experiment was accompanied by a control in which boiled enzyme was used in place of the active one. Ostwald's viscometers, thoroughly cleaned and dried, were employed for all viscometric studies. The relative viscosity with distilled water at 40° corresponded to a gravitational flow of about 58 seconds. The capillaries of the viscosimeters were specially selected so that they could be used for the reaction mixtures whose initial viscosities were comparatively high with 2% starch solution; the instrument gave a flow of about 150 to 160 seconds at 40°.

Viscosity determinations were conducted at 40° in an electrically heated and controlled thermostat. Readings were taken at known intervals of time lasting for an hour.

The Unit of α -Amylase.—One enzyme unit* is defined as that quantity of the enzyme which, acting on a 2% solution of starch (B.D.H.) at p_H 7.0 and at 40°, will bring about a 25% reduction in viscosity in 90 minutes.

Determination of the Enzyme Units.—The reaction was carried out in an Ostwald's viscometer, maintaining strictly the conditions specified above. The percentage of reduction of viscosity was plotted against time and the time course curve of the reaction was drawn. The time taken for the 25% reduction in viscosity was read off from the curve so constructed.

If the time taken for 25% reduction is 15 minutes, the enzyme preparation would contain 6 units.

Enzyme units per c c. of a given sample = $90/t$, t being the time (in minutes) for 25% reduction in viscosity.

Effect of different forms of Nitrogen on the Formation of Amylase in Bacteria.—

In order to find out the effect of different forms of nitrogen in relation to the formation of amylase in bacteria, it was found necessary to study the effect of excluding or limiting

* This has been found to be a very convenient unit since we have rarely found the activity of samples investigated falling below one unit.

the supply of oxygen in the culture media. With this end in view, two different and independent sets of experiments were conducted :

- (a) Placing culture tubes vertically and in a slanting position (25°) so that the latter set of tubes received greater degree of aerobic condition.
- (b) Blowing in a current of sterilized air through the culture medium placed in a flask.

The culture media of the following composition were employed. The results obtained at room temperature (25° - 27°) are given in Table I.

TABLE I

• Basal media	...	1.0 ml.
Starch solution (2%)	...	2.5
Nitrogen source (ammonium lactate equivalent to 2.0 mg. level of nitrogen)	...	1.0
p ⁿ	...	7.0
Volume made up to	...	10.0

* One litre of distilled water contained 1.0 g. of KH_2PO_4 , 1.0 g. of K_2HPO_4 , 0.5 g. of NaCl , 0.1 g. of CaCl_2 , 0.1 g. of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01 g. of MnSO_4 and 0.01 g. of FeSO_4 .

The data in Table II reveal interesting facts :

- (a) The culture tubes, which by virtue of their being placed in a slanting position were exposed to a higher degree of aeration, formed in themselves very nearly 4 to 5 times as much of amylase as compared with the culture tubes in the vertical position, otherwise maintained under the same conditions. The vertically placed tubes had comparatively a very limited surface exposed to air. The results indicate the essential importance of aeration in the formation of amylase.
- (b) When air was blown through the culture media, there was a 25 to 30% increase in the concentration of the enzyme formed.

TABLE II

Effect of aerobic and anaerobic conditions on the formation of bacterial amylase.

(Figures given in enzyme units per 10 ml. of the medium).

Incubation period.	a		b	
	Vertical.	Slant.	Non-aerated.	Aerated.
72 hrs.	20.8	100.5	116.2	165.2
96	24.3	114.5	134.3	188.0
120	30.7	131.2	148.8	186.0

All further experiments in this line were carried out under conditions of aeration. The method of culturing the bacteria in specially large tubes kept in a slanting position was uniformly adopted to facilitate adequate aeration of the cultures.

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FIG. 1

Time course curve of enzyme extracts from cultures grown on different sources of N without aeration.

FIG. 2

Time course curve of enzyme extracts obtained from cultures grown on different source of N with aeration.

In some cases, the effect of aeration was also studied side by side with the nitrogen series. The nitrogen level in the culture media was tried mostly at two levels e.g. 1.0 mg. and 2.0 mg. The composition of the media for these studies was the same as previously described under the aeration studies, excepting that the source of nitrogen was variant. Incubation was carried out at 37° for 72 hours. After 72 hours' growth, toluene (2 ml.) was added to each of the tubes. These tubes were then incubated at 30° for 24 hours to effect autolysis of the cells. After this period, the tubes were cen-

trifuged at 3000 r.p.m., when a clear supernatant layer was obtained. The reaction curves obtained with different amylase preparations have been plotted (time-percentage of reduction in viscosity) and the enzyme units calculated from these curves have been tabulated (Figs. 1-4 and Tables III and IV).

TABLE III

Effect of aeration on the formation of diastase.

Nitrogen source (0.7 mg. level of nitrogen).	Enzyme units for 10 c.c. of the medium.*	
	Slant.	Vertical.
1. Glutamic acid	60.0	13.0
2. Glycine	12.6	Negligible
3. KNO ₃	50.0	18.0
4. Ammonium sulphate	32.0	23.0
5. Urea	11.69	Negligible
6. Peptone	26.00	10.6
7. Wheat bran extract (papain digest)	11.25	Negligible

* Wherever found necessary, the reaction curves were extrapolated to 25% reduction in viscosity and the corresponding time noted for the determination of the enzyme unit.

TABLE IV

Effect of different forms of inorganic nitrogen on diastase formation.

(Results expressed as units of enzyme per 10 c.c. of medium at 1 and 2 mg. levels of nitrogen).

Nitrogen source.	Nitrogen level	
	1.0 mg.	2.0 mg.
Ammonium lactate	70.0	112.5
Sodium nitrate	36.0	36.0
Potassium nitrate	33.3	34.0
Ammonium nitrate	...	48.6
Ammonium sulphate		
+ sodium nitrate	40.0	44.0
Ammonium sulphate	Negligible*	Negligible *
Ammonium chloride	Do	Do

* Due to low p^H .

The following classes of compounds were investigated to ascertain the effect of the quality of nitrogen source on the formation of bacterial amylase.

(a) *Organic Forms of Nitrogen.*—Both the simpler and the more complex forms were tried as sources of nitrogen. Of the simpler organic forms of nitrogen employed, glutamic acid constituted the best source of nitrogen from the point of view of enzyme formation, while glycine gave very poor results. Wheat bran extract and peptone, both gave comparatively low results.

(b) *Inorganic Forms of Nitrogen*.—Principally two inorganic sources of nitrogen were tried, the ammonium salts and the nitrates. When ammonium salts were employed, the acidic anion residue accumulated resulting in a lowering of the p_n of the medium; with nitrates, however, the cation residue was left as a residue tending to raise the p_n of the medium. Ammonium nitrate was also tried with the expectation that both ions

FIG. 3

Effect of inorganic forms of N on the formation of diastase (2.0 mg. level).

FIG. 4

Effect of inorganic forms of N on the formation of diastase (1.0 mg. level).

might be utilised at the same rate, leaving no residual effects. The mixture of the salts, ammonium sulphate and NaNO_3 , was tried with the expectation that the p_{H} of the medium after utilisation of the nitrogen bearing ions would remain constant due to the neutralisation of the equivalent residues.

When ammonium salts of inorganic acids were employed as the source of nitrogen, e.g. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4$ and NH_4Cl , negligible quantities of diastase were formed. There was a fall in the p_{H} of the medium as it very often went down to 4.8 and the amylase, even if it were formed, would get continuously inactivated at this low p_{H} . In the case of nitrates, however, appreciable quantities of the enzyme were formed and the p_{H} rose often to a maximum of 7.6.

The best form of inorganic nitrogen appears to be ammonium lactate as evidenced by the high formation of amylase when the salt is furnished as the source of nitrogen. The p_{H} of the medium remains constant and possibly the lactic acid ion also contributes effectively towards the formation of the enzyme.

It was therefore of interest to study a series of the ammonium salts of a number of fatty acids to determine and evaluate the efficiency of the fatty acid moiety of the salt. The results of these studies are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Effect of ammonium salts of different fatty acids on the formation of diastase.

(Results expressed as units of enzyme per 10 c.c. of medium).

Nitrogen source.	Nitrogen level	
	1.0 mg.	2.0 mg.
Ammonium lactate	77.0	110.0
Ammonium citrate	58.5	104.0
Ammonium formate	...	35.5
Ammonium acetate	31.8	45.0
Ammonium propionate	22.5	7.03*
Ammonium butyrate	75.0	79.6
Ammonium gluconate	Negligible	Negligible

* Due to low p_{H} .

It appears from the table that the nature of the fatty acid associated with the ammonium salt determines the efficiency of ammonia as the source of nitrogen for diastase formation. Of the salts tried, ammonium lactate is the most efficient and the gluconate is the poor as enzyme formers.

In view of the pivotal position which lactic acid occupies in carbohydrate metabolism, it is not surprising that lactate should constitute the most efficient salt, as it may offer, in addition to the nitrogen, a highly reactive source of carbon, or carbon-containing group favouring the formation of diastase.

C O N C L U S I O N

The formation of amylase in bacteria is influenced by the type of nitrogenous compounds supplied for its nutrition.

Of all the sources of nitrogen tried, ammonium lactate has been found to be one of the best enzyme formers; its excellence is to be attributed not merely to the ammonium ion but more to its exceptional combination with an easily assimilable intermediary of carbohydrate metabolism, *i.e.* the lactate. The salt is perhaps directly utilized without leaving any toxic or inhibitory residues. Among the simple organic forms of nitrogen investigated, glutamic acid offers the best source of nitrogen for the maximum yield of the enzyme.

Aeration is found to considerably enhance the yield of amylase.

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